

Aleuritic Acid—A new Triterpene Acid from *Aleuritus montana*

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The acidic fraction from the benzene extract of the bark of *Aleurites montana* (Euphorbiaceae) on esterification with diazomethane followed by chromatography furnished in 0.005% yield a new crystalline triterpene, acetoxy methyl aleuritolate (I) $C_{33}H_{52}O_4$, mol. wt. 512 (mass), m.p. 241–3°, $[\alpha]_D + 23.08^*$, no UV absorption above 220 m μ , ν_{max}^{KBr} 1735 cm^{-1} , (broad, $-OCOCH_3$ and $-COOCH_3$), 1245 cm^{-1} , ($-OCOCH_3$), NMR signals at δ 5.50 (1H, vinyl proton, trisubstituted double bond), δ 4.46 (1H, $H-C-O-COCH_3$), δ 2.043 H, $-OCOCH_3$), δ 3.58 (3H, $-COOCH_3$) and several sharp signals between δ 0.8 to 1.65 (21H, seven CH_3 groups). Investigations described below show that it has the modified oleanane carbon skeleton consistent with the structure (I).

Hydrolysis of acetoxy methyl aleuritolate (I) with 5% methanolic potassium hydroxide furnished the alcohol (II), m.p. 208–10°, $[\alpha]_D + 11.11^*$, $\nu_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 3480 cm^{-1} ($-OH$), 1735 cm^{-1} ($-COOCH_3$); NMR signals at δ 5.50 (1H, vinyl proton, trisubstituted double bond), δ 3.54 (3H, $-COOCH_3$) and signals for methyl groups. Compound (II) on acetylation gave the acetoxy methyl aleuritolate (I) (m.m.p.). Tertiary nature of the carboxyl group was indicated by the resistance of the methyl ester toward hydrolysis with alkali (10%).

* Rotations were taken in $CHCl_3$ solution unless otherwise stated.

CrO₃-Py oxidation of hydroxy methyl ester (II) furnished the ketone (III), C₃₁H₄₆O₃, mol. wt. 468 (mass), m.p. 174-6°, $[\alpha]_D + 11.76^\circ$, ν_{max}^{KBr} 1705 cm⁻¹ (C = O), 1735 (-COOCH₃); NMR signals at δ 5.58 (1H, vinyl proton), δ 3.58 (3H, -COOCH₃) and signals for methyl protons.

Hydrolysis of the methyl ester (I) with potassium tert-butoxide in dimethyl sulphoxide by the method of Chang and Wood¹ furnished the acid (IV), m.p. 300-2°, ν_{max}^{KBr} 1700 cm⁻¹ (-COOH) for which the name aleuritolic acid is proposed.

The acetoxy methyl ester (I) showed yellow coloration with tetranitromethane. The compound (I) consumed one mole of perbenzoic acid, indicating the presence of one double bond. Acid isomerisation² of the compound (I) by heating with conc. hydrochloric acid in acetic acid for 15 min. gave a crystalline solid, m.p. 219-20°, $[\alpha]_D + 58.82^\circ$, identical with an authentic specimen of acetyl methyl oleanolate³ (m.m.p. and I.R.). This fact coupled with the NMR data establishes that the compound (I) contains a modified oleanane skeleton with a double bond.

The position of the double bond in aleuritolic acid was revealed by the mass spectra of the acetoxy methyl aleuritolate (I) and methyl aleuritolate (III). In these compounds a retro-Diels-Alder decomposition would be expected. The compounds (I) and (III) exhibit a mass peak at 344 (a) for (I) and 300 (a) for (III). This ion-peak is accompanied by a peak 15 mass units lower (b), which is formed by the loss of the methyl group, probably the allylically activated one at C-8 (b). The spectrum of (I) exhibits in addition a peak at 284 (a-CH₃COOH) and at 269 (b-CH₃COOH). In addition to species (a) and its further decomposition products, the spectra of (I) and (III) show a very abundant fragment at m/e 248 (c). This cleavage product therefore cannot contain ring A but must be derived from ring D and E. Furthermore, fragment (c) loses the substituent at C-17 giving rise to a fragment (d) 189 (c-COOCH₃). This type of fragmentation can be explained by assuming the 14 : 15 double bond in oleanane skeleton and has been found to be consistent with the mass spectral data of taraxarene derivatives reported by Carl Djerassi *et al.*⁴.

The above data are compatible with structure (IV) for aleuritolic acid and correlation with a suitable member of the oleanane series was considered. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of acetoxy methyl aleuritolate (I) furnished the corresponding diol (V), m.p. 265-67°, which was identified as myricadiol⁵⁻⁷ by direct comparison (m.m.p. and I.R.) with an authentic sample. Acetylation of the diol gave myricadiol diacetate (VI), m.p. 251-52°, $[\alpha]_D - 3^\circ$, identical with an authentic sample of myricadiol diacetate (m.m.p. and I.R.). These data establish aleuritolic acid as olean-14(15)-en-3- β -ol-28-oic acid (IV).

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